

THE NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES ON THE COMPRESSION MOLDING OF THERMOSET COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Sejin Han¹, Roy Bendickson² and Eric Henry³

¹Autodesk, 2353 North Triphammer Road, Ithaca, NY 14850, USA
Email: sejin.han@autodesk.com, web page: <http://www.autodesk.com>

²Citadel Plastics, 3365 East Center Street, Conneaut, OH 44030, USA
Email: rbendickson@citadelplastics.com, web page: <http://www.citadelplastics.com>

³Autodesk, One Discovery Place, Columbus Drive, Farnborough, Hampshire, UK
Email: eric.henry@autodesk.com, web page: <http://www.autodesk.com>

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ABSTRACT

This paper is on the analysis of compression molding of thermoset composite materials with a particular emphasis on the calculation of mechanical properties and shrinkage of the part. Accurate prediction of mechanical properties and deformation of the parts is important in the design of the part, material selection and process optimization. In this work, a simulation program is used for the compression molding process analysis. The material used in this study is a thermoset composite material (sheet molding compound) and has a high concentration of long fiber. Therefore, the fiber orientation analysis and the fiber breakage analysis are needed. The program analyzes various aspects of the compression molding process such as filling, fiber orientation, fiber length distribution, curing, mechanical properties and deformation of the part.

The experiments performed in this study include compression molding and material property measurement. Compression moldings were performed at various conditions to examine the effects of process conditions (such as mold temperature, compression force and compression time). Some material properties needed for the simulation (such as PVT data and mechanical properties) were measured. Comparison between simulation and experiment was done in terms of shrinkage of the part. The comparison shows reasonable agreement between simulation and experiment.

1 INTRODUCTION

In compression molding, some portion of the cavity is initially filled by an initial charge. The initial cavity thickness is much higher than the final part thickness [1]. The mold cavity thickness is reduced by a compressive force, forcing the resin and reinforcement into the unfilled portions of the cavity. After the cavity is filled, additional press movement may be required to compensate for polymer shrinkage. This compression molding process results in more homogeneous physical properties and less molded-in stresses compared to conventional injection molding. Also, for long fiber, compression molding has an advantage in that the final fiber length will have much less breakage than that obtained from injection molding where attrition in injection unit and feed system can occur. Long fiber composites processed by compression molding will retain most of their original fiber length leading to enhanced mechanical properties compared to short fiber composites [1].

In this study, a three-dimensional compression analysis program is used to analyze the compression molding process for thermoset materials. This program can predict the flow pattern, fiber

orientation, fiber length distribution, mechanical properties and part shrinkage. Fiber content, length and orientation greatly affect the performance of the product. Designers and engineers can use the results from the program developed in this study to optimize the materials and process conditions.

In the next sections, an analysis method for the compression process for flow and deformation calculation will be given. This will be followed by some results from a case study. In the case study, the deformation (shrinkage) of the part obtained from experiment and simulation will be compared. The effects of process conditions on part deformation will also be examined.

2 GOVERNING EQUATIONS FOR FLOW

We need to solve the following set of equations to analyze the flow during compression molding process for thermoset materials [2]:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{g} \quad (2)$$

$$\rho C_p \frac{DT}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) + \eta \dot{\gamma}^2 + \beta T \frac{Dp}{Dt} + H_r \frac{D\alpha}{Dt} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{D\alpha}{Dt} = (K_1 + K_2 \alpha^\mu)(1 - \alpha)^\nu \quad (4)$$

where

$$K_1 = A_1 e^{(-\frac{E_1}{T})} \quad K_2 = A_2 e^{(-\frac{E_2}{T})} \quad (5)$$

Equation (1) is the mass continuity equation, (2) the momentum equation and (3) the energy equation. Equations (4) and (5) curing kinetics equations due to Kamal [3]. In the above equations, ρ is density, t time, \mathbf{v} velocity, p pressure, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ stress tensor, \mathbf{g} gravitational constant of the earth. Also, C_p is the heat capacity, T temperature, k thermal conductivity, η viscosity, $\dot{\gamma}$ shear rate, β expansivity and H_r heat of reaction. Furthermore, α is degree of cure and $A_1, A_2, E_1, E_2, \mu, \nu$ are constants used in the curing kinetics.

As for the boundary conditions, a specified speed boundary condition needs to be applied at the compression mold wall when the press is moving under speed control. When the press is moving under force control, the press speed needs to be calculated based on the press force.

The fiber-orientation, fiber-length distribution and mechanical property calculations were done as described in [4] – [8].

3 MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Several material properties (such as viscosity, curing kinetics, PVT data, thermal properties and mechanical properties) are needed for the analysis of compression molding process. For the PVT (pressure-volume-temperature relation), we use the following Tait equation for the uncured phase [9]:

$$v_u = v_{0u} \left(1 - C \ln\left(1 + \frac{P}{B_u(T)}\right)\right) \quad (6)$$

$$v_{0u} = b_{1,u} + b_{2,u} \bar{T}_u \quad \text{if } T > T_u \quad (7)$$

$$v_{0u} = b_{1,su} + b_{2,su} \bar{T}_u \quad \text{if } T < T_{tu} \quad (8)$$

$$B_u(T) = b_{3,lu} \exp(-b_{4,lu} \bar{T}_u) \quad \text{if } T > T_{tu} \quad (9)$$

$$B_u(T) = b_{3,su} \exp(-b_{4,su} \bar{T}_u) \quad \text{if } T < T_{tu} \quad (10)$$

$$T_{tu} = b_{5u} + b_{6u} p \quad (11)$$

$$\bar{T}_u = T - b_{5u} \quad (12)$$

where v_u is the specific volume of the uncured phase, and $C = 0.0894$. b_1 , b_2 , b_3 , b_4 , b_5 and b_6 are parameters obtained from the fitting experimental data. Subscript s represents solid state (below transition temperature) and l represents liquid state. Similar equations can be used for cured phase. For intermediate cure phase, the following equation is used (v is the specific volume of intermediate cure phase and v_c is the specific volume of cured phase):

$$1/v = (1/v_u)(1 - \alpha) + (1/v_c)\alpha \quad (13)$$

4 AN EXAMPLE CASE

In this study, the part shown in Figure 1 is used for the compression molding. The following standard process conditions are used in the molding of this part. The initial melt temperature is 45°C, and the mold temperature is 143 °C. The nominal fill time is about 13 seconds. The maximum press force (compression tonnage) is 272 metric tons. The compression is switched to force control near the end of filling. After that, the press force is maintained at the compression tonnage for 150 seconds. The press moves at a controlled speed until switch over to force control. The initial press speed is at 3.5 mm/sec, but it drops with time as shown in Figure 2. After switch over to force control, the press moves at a constant press force. The polymer used is a thermoset sheet molding compound (SMC) from Premix (Premi-Glas 1286). This is a composite material with 34% glass fiber by weight (with a mixture of fibers with initial fiber length of 12.7 mm and 25.4 mm).

Figure 1: A geometry model for the part used in the current study.

Figure 2: Press speed profile used in the compression molding.

Experiments were conducted to measure the deformation of the part after the molding. Some process conditions were varied to examine the effects of process conditions on the part deformation. Mold temperature, press force and compression time (after the end of filling) in the molding were varied as shown in Table 1.

Molding case	Mold temperature (C)	Compression force (metric ton)	Compression time (sec)
1 (Standard)	143	272	150
2 (Lower mold temperature)	132	272	150
3 (Higher mold temperature)	154	272	150
4 (Lower compression force)	143	204	150
5 (Shorter compression time)	143	272	120
6 (Longer compression time)	143	272	180

Table 1: Process conditions used in the compression molding experiments.

The PVT data of the resin were measured using a Gnomix PVT testing machine. The measured results at various pressure values (0 – 30 MPa) are shown in Figure 3 for the cured sample. The PVT data shows two regions of different slopes with a transition temperature around 130 °C. The PVT data for uncured sample has the same slope as the cured sample except that 25 °C is used as the transition temperature.

Figure 3: PVT data for the cured phase of the molding material (the values in the legend are pressure in MPa). The symbols are experimental data and the lines are fitting using the Tait equation.

The mechanical properties of the cured sample were determined by molding the samples, and then by measuring the elastic properties using the tensile testing machine in different directions. The mechanical properties thus determined are shown in Table 2.

Property	Value
Elastic modulus in 1 st principal direction [MPa]	24900
Elastic modulus in 2nd principal direction [MPa]	6350
Poisson's ratio (ν ₁₂)	0.267
Poisson's ratio (ν ₂₃)	0.346
Shear modulus [MPa]	2638

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the cured sample.

Deformation (shrinkage) measurements of the molded parts were done as shown in Figure 4. It measured the shrinkage in X and Y directions. The shrinkage in X direction was determined by measuring the distance between A-B in the part and comparing it with the distance in the mold. The shrinkage in Y direction was determined by measuring the distances C-D and E-F and comparing the average value with the distance in the mold. The measured part shrinkage values in X and Y directions are shown in Table 3 (where the shrinkage values obtained from simulation are also shown which will be described later). The distance A-B in the mold is about 801.9 mm and the distance C-D or E-F is about 214.1 mm. As can be seen in Table 3, the average experimental shrinkage in X-direction is about 1.39 mm. In terms of %shrinkage, it is about 0.173%. On the other hand, the average experimental shrinkage in Y-direction is about 0.583 mm (in terms of %shrinkage, it is about 0.272%).

Figure 4: Deformation (shrinkage) measurement locations (A-B, C-D and E - F).

Molding case	Shrinkage X (Experiment) [mm]	Shrinkage X (Simulation) [mm]	Shrinkage Y (Experiment) [mm]	Shrinkage Y (Simulation) [mm]
1 (Standard)	1.399	1.26	0.522	0.72
2 (Lower mold temperature)	1.081	1.09	0.535	0.69
3 (Higher mold temperature)	1.478	1.37	0.722	0.79
4 (Lower compression force)	1.716	1.35	0.598	0.76
5 (Shorter compression time)	1.399	1.29	0.669	0.74
6 (Longer compression time)	1.240	1.25	0.453	0.72

Table 3: Measured and calculated shrinkage values in X (A-B) and Y-directions (average of C-D/E-F).

As for the simulation, the software developed in this study was used to simulate the molding process. Figure 5 shows the simulation model for the initial charge and the part. In this figure, the green area is the final shape of the part to be molded, and the gray area is the initial charge. The length of the part is about 800 mm, the width is 200 mm and the typical thickness of the final part is about 4 mm. The finite-element mesh has approximately 1,585,000 tetrahedral elements and 276,000 nodes. For the fiber-orientation analysis, the RSC model was used (with the value of interaction parameter of 0.1 and RSC parameter of 0.05). The high value of the interaction parameter was chosen to account for the strong interaction between fibers for the current case. The initial fiber orientation in the initial charge was random in the plane (X-Y direction).

Figure 5: A simulation model which shows the part (green) and the initial charge (gray).

The simulation results are shown in Figures 6 - 12. The results are for the standard process condition unless stated otherwise.

Figure 6 shows the degree of cure distribution at the end of molding. Degree of cure value ranges from 0 to 1 (1 being the complete cure). As can be seen from this figure, the degree of cure at the outer edge is smaller than the center region. This is because the material at the outer edge is at high temperature for a shorter time than the one in the center region.

Figure 6: Calculated degree of cure distribution at the end of molding.

Figure 7 shows the average volumetric shrinkage of the part at the end of molding (in %). The average value is through the thickness. It shows that the volumetric shrinkage value at the outer edge is bigger than the center region because the degree of cure at that region is lower than the center region at the end of molding.

Figure 7: Calculated average volumetric shrinkage distribution at the end of molding..

Figure 8 shows the fiber orientation tensor results obtained from simulation. In this plot, the direction of the long bar represents the direction of the first principal value of orientation. If the value is high (close to 1), it means that more of the fibers are aligned in the first principal direction. The plot shows that near the center of the part (where the initial charge is located), the fiber orientation value is about 0.5 (representing random orientation). Away from the center, the orientation value is higher indicating some alignment in some direction.

Figure 8: Calculated fiber orientation tensor values.

Figure 9 shows the fiber length distribution obtained from the simulation. The composite material has fibers of initial length 12.7 mm and 25.4 mm. In this simulation, we used the average of the two values (19 mm) as the initial fiber length. As can be seen from this figure, the fiber length at the end of molding is 17 mm or higher in most regions which are close to the initial length (19 mm). This indicates that there is not much fiber breakage for this case. It also shows that the fiber becomes shorter away from the center.

Figure 9: Fiber-length distribution in the cavity (in mm).

Figure 10 shows the calculated tensile modulus in the first principal direction. Figure 11 is the calculated Poisson's ratio. In these calculations, the fiber length obtained in Figure 9 is used. Since there is not much fiber breakage, the mechanical properties are expected to be similar to those with initial fiber length for this case.

Figure 10: Calculated tensile modulus in the first principal direction (in MPa).

Figure 11: Calculated Poisson's ratio (v_{12}).

Figure 12 shows the calculated deformation of the part. Figure 12(a) is for the X-direction, and Figure 12(b) is for the Y-direction. From these results, the shrinkage values in X and Y directions are determined using the locations shown in Figure 4. The calculated results are compared with the experimental results in Table 3 above. As can be seen from Table 3, the calculated results and the experimental results compare well. As for the effects of process conditions, the simulation results show the following:

- (1) Lower mold temperature reduces the shrinkage. This is because of the smaller temperature change during cooling from the mold temperature to the room temperature after the molding

which results in smaller shrinkage value. However, if the mold temperature is too low, it may result in under-cure of the part which may increase the shrinkage.

- (2) As for the press force, lower press force increases the shrinkage. This is obvious from the PVT relation of the resin.
- (3) As for the compression (or curing) time, longer compression time reduces the shrinkage. This is because longer curing time increases the degree of cure of the sample at the end of molding and this reduces the shrinkage of the part. However, the simulation results indicate that this effect is small.

The experimental results generally show the similar trends in terms of the effects of the process conditions.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12: Deformation values calculated in (a) X and (b) Y direction.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, compression molding with thermoset materials was analyzed using a numerical simulation. Some calculation results were compared with experimental results. In particular, the part shrinkage values from the simulation matched reasonably well with the experimental results

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